

Report on 2023 CLARIN-CH Survey

Anonymized, 07.04.2024

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(1) Short Report – CLARIN-CH Survey Results

Overview

The survey gathered responses from **92 participants**, with **all Swiss Higher Education Institutions (HEIs)** in the CLARIN-CH Consortium represented. The results provide a comprehensive picture of awareness, usage, needs, and engagement with CLARIN and its Swiss node CLARIN-CH infrastructure and services.

Key Findings

1. Awareness and Use of CLARIN

- Respondents show **moderate familiarity** with the CLARIN infrastructure.
- **Actual use of CLARIN resources and tools remains limited**, indicating a gap between awareness and adoption.
- Reported barriers include:
 - Lack of knowledge about available services
 - Uncertainty about access procedures
 - Limited integration into existing workflows

2. Training Needs

Training emerged as a **major priority**:

- Strong demand for **practical, hands-on training** in:
 - NLP tools (e.g., POS tagging, lemmatization, sentiment analysis)
 - Data preparation, cleaning, and processing
- Need for **introductory overviews** of CLARIN services and how they interconnect
- Interest in:
 - Access policies and legal aspects
 - Using datasets for teaching
 - Discoverability and effective reuse of resources

3. Sharing of Language Resources

- Participants are **actively developing language resources and tools**, but:
 - Sharing practices are **not yet systematic**
 - Concerns exist around **data protection, legal compliance, and sustainability**
- There is clear interest in **better infrastructure for sharing and long-term preservation**

4. Working Groups and Collaboration

- There is **strong interest in national cross-institutional working groups (WGs)**
- Suggested themes include:
 - Digital Humanities and multimodal corpora
 - Semantics and translation studies
 - Literary stylistics
 - Dialectology and historical corpora
- Some participants are willing to **take leadership roles**, indicating good potential for community building

5. Disciplinary Needs

Respondents highlighted a wide range of needs:

a) Data Management & Legal Support

- Standards for metadata, transcription, and corpus design
- Guidance on **FAIR data principles** and best practices
- Strong demand for **legal support** (GDPR, consent, anonymization)
- Solutions for **sensitive data handling and secure storage**

b) Language Resources

- Access to **large, diverse, and multimodal corpora**
- Sustainability and long-term availability of resources
- Improved access to **spoken, sign, and social media data**

c) Language Technology

- Access to **NLP tools and reusable components**
- Need for **annotation tools, phonetic tools, and HPC resources**
- Interest in **AI/NLP model development and reuse**

d) Collaboration

- Desire for **interdisciplinary and cross-lingual collaboration**
- Support for **joint corpus building and shared infrastructures**

e) Training & Support

- Training in:
 - Corpus building
 - Coding and data analysis
 - Statistical methods
- Demand for **expert guidance throughout research lifecycles**

6. Awareness of National Infrastructure

- Awareness of key national components (e.g., Linguistic Research Infrastructure LiRI, Language Repository of Switzerland LaRS) is **uneven and generally limited**
- Indicates a need for **better visibility and communication of national services**

7. Engagement in CLARIN-CH Activities

- **A significant proportion of respondents expressed willingness to engage more actively**
- This suggests strong potential for:
 - Community development
 - Co-creation of services
 - Increased adoption of CLARIN infrastructure

Conclusions

The survey highlights a **clear gap between available infrastructure and its effective use**. The main priorities for CLARIN-CH moving forward are:

1. **Training and capacity building** (especially hands-on and practical)
2. **Improved communication and visibility** of services
3. **Support for data management, legal compliance, and sensitive data**
4. **Facilitation of collaboration through thematic working groups**
5. **Strengthening resource sharing and sustainability mechanisms**

Overall, the results show a **strong and engaged research community**, with high expectations and clear directions for the future development of CLARIN-CH.

(3) Acquaintance with the CLARIN infrastructure

(4) Use of CLARIN resources and infrastructure components

Reasons for not using the CLARIN infrastructure

■ I already have the language resources and NLP tools I need. (16%) ■ I have not thought of searching on the CLARIN website. (41%)

■ I do not know how to access and use the resources/tools/services existent in the CLARIN infrastructure. (26%) ■ Other. Please fill in what other reason(s). (17%)

(5) Training needs

Need of training in using a specific service or tool/software available in the CLARIN-EU infrastructure

Specific needs for training regarding the CLARIN infrastructure

- Understanding access policies
- Preparation, cleaning, and processing of large datasets with current NLP tools preparation of datasets for use in teaching
- Part-of-speech tagging and lemmatization Tools for sentiment analysis
- NLP tools for POS tagging if any available
- NLP tools and possible services from CLARIN infrastructure
- Not specific, just global overview
- Newspaper data, statistics and linguistic maps
- Accessing all resources and services (mostly, knowing what they are and how they can be interconnected) and how to exploit them at their full potential

(6) Sharing of language resources

Development of language resources, NLP tools or other type of resources that can be shared within CLARIN-CH and CLARIN

(7) National CLARIN-CH Working Groups

Interest in getting involved in a national cross-institutional thematic CLARIN-CH Working Group (WG)

Ideas for CLARIN-CH national thematic WGs

■ Dialectology. Language variation. Language typology. (23%) ■ Speech and Language technology applied to business (11%)

■ None of these working groups is of interest for me. (11%) ■ Language and medicine (18%) ■ Research infrastructures for Argumentation and Rhetoric (13%)

■ Applied linguistics. Language teaching. (25%)

Would you be interested in taking the lead in a CLARIN-CH WG that is of interest for you?

You have answered that none of the suggested CLARIN-CH WGs is of interest for you. Please, fill in your proposition of one or more WGs below:

- There is a current project on complex interactional data that could constitute such a WG. The results of this WG might be of interest for other CLARIN members
- Text Oriented Digital Humanities Language and (digital) Society Multimodal Corpora
- Anything with semantics
- Translation Studies
- Literary stylistics
- Dialectology, variation, historical. If not, a WG on historical corpora and databases would be of great interest (also potential link with DARIAH-CH). I would also be interested in a group that deals with heritage language data.

(8) Disciplinary needs

What are the specific needs of your discipline (access to research infrastructures, specific metadata and standards, sensitive data, etc.) to which you like to draw the attention of the CLARIN-CH Consortium?

About data management

- Standards for historical corpora, databases (standards, sensitive data) linked to heritage linguistics
- Best practices of data management and documentation, including help in the conceptual stages of data collection/corpus development.
- Sensitive data
- Provide long-term storage solutions for linguistic resources

- Methods of handling and archiving language data and also access to corpora.
- Bespoke metadata and adaptability to corpus specific characteristics
- Help with legal issues (maybe counselling or design and share model documents) when collecting (user) data or dealing with sensitive data from interviews to be compliant with GDPR, e.g., what to include in consent forms, how to anonymize/pseudonymize user information
- Coordinating of national accepted standard for data preservation and curation
- Sensitive data from interviews, screen recordings and experiments. I cannot share the corpora I worked with, because of data protection issues.
- Sustainability of digital resources for linguistics beyond the lifetime of individual projects
- Data storage
- Specific metadata, e.g. translation memories standards
- Host linguistic data (e.g. collection of native speakers' judgments about some linguistic properties of their language) on a data repository complying with the FAIR Data Principles
- Guidelines about data management
- Data standards
- Legal questions in the context of making corpora open access.
- Transcription standards; metadata storing
- Data repositories
- Platform to store sensitive data obtained through experiments; platform like OSF to publish experimental items etc. to ensure transparency of experiments.
- Another key issue concerns the ethics of corpora building and circulation
- Data storage

About language resources

- Access to shared resources
- Provide long-term storage solutions for linguistic resources.
- Make learner texts accessible and searchable
- Access to larger corpora to study the use of gender inclusive language
- Collaboration with Chinese databases
- Multimodal corpora, digital editions, social media corpora
- Access to corpus data, tools for corpus annotation
- Sustainable access of resources, in particular for resources generated within time-bound projects
- Access to sensitive data, especially for teaching, for instance with speakers having language disorders
- Spoken language data and sign language and multimodal data

About language technology

- Development of existing language models (mBERT)
- NLP and query tools
- Automatic phonetic segmentation tools
- Access to high performance computing for indexing and automatic annotation of corpus data (i.e., only for certain amounts of time not regularly);
- A reflection on the criteria for designing corpora to make them exploitable by new NLP approaches, in particular concerning complex corpora (articulation text, audio, video).
- Access to previously developed tools for reuse in new research projects
- Scarcity of corpora when it comes to particular NLP tasks (i.e., text simplification datasets, especially in the context of French).
- Psycho- and neuro-linguistics tools
- Free (and working!) tools for annotation
- Access to and support in corpus analysis tools

About fostering collaboration

- Extended collaboration with colleagues working in similar/the same field, but with different languages / methods
- It would be wonderful to have a group of experts at hand who could help with the individual planification of the technical and legal aspects which have to be considered when submitting a proposal to the SNSF.
- Collaboration for corpus building, shared corpora
- Inter- and transdisciplinary collaboration (working on language data with non-linguists)

About providing support and training

- Training and support in corpus building
- Basic training in coding for research purposes (e. g., for data analysis and basic tools development)
- Learn more about other technologies that I don't use yet
- Training in statistics tools for linguists

Access and development of RIs

- Access to the field (i.e. the schools) because in my canton the access to language classrooms is extremely limited.
- Access to research infrastructures, development of new research infrastructures,
- My discipline is not a single discipline. It consists of expertise from linguistics, phonetics, engineering, psychology, neurosciences, computer sciences, biology, medicine, etc. My specific needs are top bring people form this interdisciplinary array of paradigms together which share the central aim to understand human vocal communication with speech, in particular the processing of vocal identity.
- Inclusion and prioritization of a language focus on r4d type approaches based on multilingual university infrastructure as one of the assets of Swiss research institutions
- A pressing issue is to develop models for *online testing practices* for large group of test takers which take into consideration good academic conduct (e.g. hinder plagiat, stop test takers from cheating). I guess this is a burning issue to everybody involved in teaching in higher education.
- Create disciplinary platforms

(9) Acquaintance with national infrastructure components

To what extent are you acquainted with the Linguistic Research Infrastructure LiRI, which is one of the main partners of CLARIN-CH, as well as the services it proposes?

To what extent are you acquainted with the Language Repository of Switzerland LaRS, which is one of the main partners of CLARIN-CH, as well as the services it proposes?

(10) Involvement in CLARIN-CH activities

Would you like to get actively involved in the planning and organization of CLARIN-CH activities?

